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FINDING COMMON GROUND IN CROSS-BOUNDARY COLLABORATION

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Topics: New Notions of Interdisciplinarity in Engineering Education

Keywords: interdisciplinarity, active learning, teamwork

What are session participants expected to learn?

The workshop aims to:

- Describe and improve an existing pedagogical scenario to establish common ground in a project-based/interdisciplinary program
- Explore alternative scenarios to establish common ground in cross-boundary collaboration

Why is the session relevant?

Students need to cope with multiple perspectives to address problems as a system and solve them comprehensively [1]. At the same time team diversity is also associated with higher levels of dissatisfaction, turnover, ... and stress [2]. Collaboration is difficult because each profession has its own language, terminology, beliefs about relative importance of performance attributes, approaches to learning, mechanisms for information exchange, goals, and reward structure. In other words, the promises of cross-boundary collaboration are as large as the perils [3].

How are session participants activated?

In the first part of the workshop participants will be asked to discuss the strengths and weaknesses of an existing scenario with the aim to improve it. In the second part they will be asked to explore alternative scenarios to foster cross-boundary collaboration.

How will results be summarized?

Participants will receive a description of the existing pedagogical scenario as well as the suggested improvements. In addition, a synthesis of the alternative scenarios will be provided.

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